

COVER SHEET FOR PROPOSAL TO THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION

PROGRAM ANNOUNCEMENT/SOLICITATION NO./CLOSING DATE/if not in response to a program announcement/solicitation enter NSF 04-23					FOR NSF USE ONLY	
FOR CONSIDERATION BY NSF ORGANIZATION UNIT(S) (Indicate the most specific unit known, i.e. program, division, etc.)					NSF PROPOSAL NUMBER	
ARC - ARCTIC RESRCH SUPPRT & LOGISTI					0734931	
DATE RECEIVED	NUMBER OF COPIES	DIVISION ASSIGNED	FUND CODE	DUNS# (Data Universal Numbering System)	FILE LOCATION	
04/11/2007	2	14010000 ARC	5205	796268548	04/24/2007 9:41pm S	
EMPLOYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (EIN) OR TAXPAYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (TIN)		SHOW PREVIOUS AWARD NO. IF THIS IS <input type="checkbox"/> A RENEWAL <input type="checkbox"/> AN ACCOMPLISHMENT-BASED RENEWAL		IS THIS PROPOSAL BEING SUBMITTED TO ANOTHER FEDERAL AGENCY? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> IF YES, LIST ACRONYM(S)		
		0101279				
NAME OF ORGANIZATION TO WHICH AWARD SHOULD BE MADE			ADDRESS OF AWARDEE ORGANIZATION, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			
AWARDEE ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)			3535 College Road, Suite 101			
5300001191			Fairbanks, AK. 997093710			
NAME OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT FROM ABOVE			ADDRESS OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
PERFORMING ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)						
IS AWARDEE ORGANIZATION (Check All That Apply) (See GPG II.C For Definitions)		<input type="checkbox"/> SMALL BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> FOR-PROFIT ORGANIZATION		<input type="checkbox"/> MINORITY BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> WOMAN-OWNED BUSINESS		<input type="checkbox"/> IF THIS IS A PRELIMINARY PROPOSAL THEN CHECK HERE
TITLE OF PROPOSED PROJECT Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program						
REQUESTED AMOUNT \$	PROPOSED DURATION (1-60 MONTHS)	REQUESTED STARTING DATE	SHOW RELATED PRELIMINARY PROPOSAL NO. IF APPLICABLE			
633,392	3 months					
CHECK APPROPRIATE BOX(ES) IF THIS PROPOSAL INCLUDES ANY OF THE ITEMS LISTED BELOW						
<input type="checkbox"/> BEGINNING INVESTIGATOR (GPG I.A)			<input type="checkbox"/> HUMAN SUBJECTS (GPG II.D.6)			
<input type="checkbox"/> DISCLOSURE OF LOBBYING ACTIVITIES (GPG II.C)			Exemption Subsection _____ or IRB App. Date _____			
<input type="checkbox"/> PROPRIETARY & PRIVILEGED INFORMATION (GPG I.B, II.C.1.d)			<input type="checkbox"/> INTERNATIONAL COOPERATIVE ACTIVITIES: COUNTRY/COUNTRIES INVOLVED (GPG II.C.2.j)			
<input type="checkbox"/> HISTORIC PLACES (GPG II.C.2.j)						
<input type="checkbox"/> SMALL GRANT FOR EXPLOR. RESEARCH (SGER) (GPG II.D.1)			<input type="checkbox"/> HIGH RESOLUTION GRAPHICS/OTHER GRAPHICS WHERE EXACT COLOR REPRESENTATION IS REQUIRED FOR PROPER INTERPRETATION (GPG I.G.1)			
<input type="checkbox"/> VERTEBRATE ANIMALS (GPG II.D.5) IACUC App. Date _____						
PI/PD DEPARTMENT		PI/PD POSTAL ADDRESS				
ARCUS		3535 College Road, Suite 101				
PI/PD FAX NUMBER		Fairbanks, AK 997093710				
907-474-1604		United States				
NAMES (TYPED)	High Degree	Yr of Degree	Telephone Number	Electronic Mail Address		
PI/PD NAME						
Wendy K Warnick	HS	1973	907-474-1600	warnick@arcus.org		
CO-PI/PD						
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CERTIFICATION PAGE

Certification for Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant:

By signing and submitting this proposal, the individual applicant or the authorized official of the applicant institution is: (1) certifying that statements made herein are true and complete to the best of his/her knowledge; and (2) agreeing to accept the obligation to comply with NSF award terms and conditions if an award is made as a result of this application. Further, the applicant is hereby providing certifications regarding debarment and suspension, drug-free workplace, and lobbying activities (see below), as set forth in Grant Proposal Guide (GPG), NSF 04-23. Willful provision of false information in this application and its supporting documents or in reports required under an ensuing award is a criminal offense (U. S. Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

In addition, if the applicant institution employs more than fifty persons, the authorized official of the applicant institution is certifying that the institution has implemented a written and enforced conflict of interest policy that is consistent with the provisions of Grant Policy Manual Section 510; that to the best of his/her knowledge, all financial disclosures required by that conflict of interest policy have been made; and that all identified conflicts of interest will have been satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated prior to the institution's expenditure of any funds under the award, in accordance with the institution's conflict of interest policy. Conflicts which cannot be satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated must be disclosed to NSF.

Drug Free Work Place Certification

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Drug Free Work Place Certification contained in Appendix C of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Debarment and Suspension Certification

(If answer "yes", please provide explanation.)

Is the organization or its principals presently debarred, suspended, proposed for debarment, declared ineligible, or voluntarily excluded from covered transactions by any Federal department or agency?

Yes

No

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Debarment and Suspension Certification contained in Appendix D of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Lobbying

This certification is required for an award of a Federal contract, grant, or cooperative agreement exceeding \$100,000 and for an award of a Federal loan or a commitment providing for the United States to insure or guarantee a loan exceeding \$150,000.

Certification for Contracts, Grants, Loans and Cooperative Agreements

The undersigned certifies, to the best of his or her knowledge and belief, that:

(1) No federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid, by or on behalf of the undersigned, to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with the awarding of any federal contract, the making of any Federal grant, the making of any Federal loan, the entering into of any cooperative agreement, and the extension, continuation, renewal, amendment, or modification of any Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement.

(2) If any funds other than Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with this Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement, the undersigned shall complete and submit Standard Form-LLL, "Disclosure of Lobbying Activities," in accordance with its instructions.

(3) The undersigned shall require that the language of this certification be included in the award documents for all subawards at all tiers including subcontracts, subgrants, and contracts under grants, loans, and cooperative agreements and that all subrecipients shall certify and disclose accordingly.

This certification is a material representation of fact upon which reliance was placed when this transaction was made or entered into. Submission of this certification is a prerequisite for making or entering into this transaction imposed by section 1352, Title 31, U.S. Code. Any person who fails to file the required certification shall be subject to a civil penalty of not less than \$10,000 and not more than \$100,000 for each such failure.

AUTHORIZED ORGANIZATIONAL REPRESENTATIVE		SIGNATURE	DATE
NAME Wendy K Warnick		Electronic Signature	Apr 11 2007 12:43AM
TELEPHONE NUMBER 907-474-1600	ELECTRONIC MAIL ADDRESS warnick@arcus.org	FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604	

*SUBMISSION OF SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBERS IS VOLUNTARY AND WILL NOT AFFECT THE ORGANIZATION'S ELIGIBILITY FOR AN AWARD. HOWEVER, THEY ARE AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE INFORMATION SYSTEM AND ASSIST IN PROCESSING THE PROPOSAL. SSN SOLICITED UNDER NSF ACT OF 1950, AS AMENDED.

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. ARC-0101279). The supplement of \$633,392 to the funds already awarded is necessary to continue support of ongoing activities that are within the scope of the original agreement while details of a new cooperative agreement are negotiated. This supplement request also extends the expiration date of the award from 31 March 2007 to 30 June 2007 so that there will be no interruption of ongoing services and current tasking prior to a new award being made.

The activities described in this request for supplemental funds fall under the following major tasks identified in the cooperative agreement: 1) Arctic Community Science Planning; 2) NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination; 3) Arctic Science Education; 4) Information and Outreach; and 5) Core Support. The activities described here provide community science management for NSF-funded research programs, coordinate research-focused community workshops and meetings, expand education and outreach opportunities for undergraduate and graduate students and for teachers and researchers, and provide important information to scientists, educators, and policy makers. All of the activities support community science planning or provide information and support for the conduct of arctic research.

Accomplishments between April 2006 and the present are outlined only for those activities for which supplemental funding is requested. This information is included to provide context for the work that ARCUS is doing through this cooperative agreement and the basis on which supplemental funding is requested. The projected activities between April and June 2007 and those activities for which supplemental funding is requested also are summarized. All activities described fall under the current scope and tasks of the existing cooperative agreement.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.4 Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Planning and Coordination

As the SEARCH science management office, ARCUS has worked since 2005 with the NSF SEARCH Program Director, the SEARCH Interagency Program Management Committee (IPMC), SEARCH Science Steering Committee (SSC) Chair and committee members, and the international arctic research community to implement a number of development and planning activities on behalf of the SEARCH program. Since April 2006, these include convening an SSC meeting, coordinating with community and agency representatives to implement recommendations of the 2005 SEARCH Implementation Workshop, and assistance with developing international collaborations such as SEARCH IPY activities

Accomplishments

- Worked with SSC and IPMC Chairs to organize and convene a SSC Meeting in Arlington, VA, in November 2006; agency personnel and members of the three SEARCH Panels also attended.
- Coordinated the creation and appointment, and facilitated activities of, three standing SEARCH Working Groups on Data Management, Paleoenvironment, and Education and Outreach.

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- Worked with the SEARCH SSC Chair and IPMC to implement membership rotation for the SSC and support appropriate SSC science planning activities, including coordination with the developing Arctic Observing Network and International Polar Year efforts.
 - Facilitated activities of the three SEARCH panels (Observing, Understanding, and Responding to Change), including supporting the development of a document detailing the design of a SEARCH observing system; the document will be a joint product of the Observing Change Panel, the SSC, and the IPMC.
 - Continued assistance with international coordination activities, including support of the Chair of the International ASOF Program and the developing partnership between SEARCH and the European Developing Arctic Modeling and Observing Capabilities for Long-term Environmental Studies (DAMOCLES).
 - Commenced planning for 2008 State of the Arctic Conference and began discussions on timing, focus, and content of conference.
 - Continued development of searchable online SEARCH Project Catalog to track and communicate SEARCH-funded and SEARCH-related research projects, initiatives, and programs, in consultation with an *ad hoc* committee.
 - Ongoing SEARCH website development and updates.

Planned Activities; Supplemental Funds Requested

The requested supplemental funding will support several continuing SEARCH planning and coordination activities, including:

- Continued development of the SEARCH Project Catalog.
- Development of a website, within the SEARCH website, for the Arctic Observing Network, a major implementation of the SEARCH Observing Change scientific priorities.
- Travel support for the SEARCH SSC Chair.
- Planning for the 2007 SEARCH SSC meeting.
- Planning for the 2008 State of the Arctic conference in 2008.
- Other project office tasks such as teleconferences, as necessary.

1.5 Bering Ecosystem Research Program Planning and Coordination

For the past several years the NSF Arctic Sciences Section has supported the Bering Ecosystem Study (BEST), a planning process to initiate collaborative studies of the sub-arctic seas, culminating in cooperative ecological research of the eastern, western, and basin areas by Japan, Russia and the United States. ARCUS provides organizational support and coordination of activities for the BEST science planning process, including support for the BEST Science Steering Committee (SSC) and coordination with the BEST planning office at the University of Washington. BEST priorities for research, published in the BEST science plan in 2004, were included in the Fall 2005 NSF Arctic Sciences Section announcement of opportunity; awards through this opportunity were announced in July 2006. ARCUS has provided continuing organizational support to the program, including convening a meeting in July 2006 of multiple agencies with research interests in the Bering Sea and a meeting in September 2006 of funded BEST principal investigators. Tasks have also included coordination and support for representatives of the program to attend a number of relevant meetings.

The requested supplemental funding will support a minimal amount of staff time for activities already funded through the existing cooperative agreement, including editing and publishing *Sustaining the Bering Ecosystem: A Social Sciences Research Plan* and travel support for program representatives.

Accomplishments

- In close collaboration with the BEST SSC, the NSF program officer, and other agency representatives, ARCUS planned, convened, and staffed a meeting in July 2006 of multiple entities with research interests in the Bering Sea: the BEST SSC, the Bering Interagency Working Group, and the Bering Interagency Oversight Group. The meeting was held on the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) campus in Seattle, Washington. 34 invited participants attended, and about 15 NOAA personnel dropped in to sessions.
- Planned, convened, and staffed a meeting of funded BEST Principal Investigators and representatives of the BEST SSC in September 2006 in Arlington, VA, to coordinate the development of an integrated research program and to guide fieldwork.
- Coordinated travel arrangements and provided materials and travel support for PIs or representatives of the BEST SSC to attend a number of relevant meetings, including the PICES-Ecosystems of Sub-arctic Seas (ESSAS) workshop in St. Petersburg, Russia (June 2006), the Calista Elders Council in Bethel, Alaska (January 2007), the Alaska Marine Science Symposium in Anchorage, Alaska (January 2007), the American Society for Limnology and Oceanography in Santa Fe, New Mexico (February 2007), and the Alaska Forum on the Environment in Anchorage, Alaska (February 2007).

Planned Activities; Currently Funded

- Assisting in planning, coordinating travel arrangements, and providing materials and travel support for PIs and representatives of the BEST SSC to attend ESSAS workshop in Hakodate, Japan (June 2007).
- Editing, publication, and dissemination of BEST social science plan, in close collaboration with members of the organizing committee
- Ongoing distribution of the BEST science and implementation plans and website maintenance and updating.

Planned Activities; Supplemental Funds Requested

- Minimal funds are requested to support additional staff time to accomplish currently funded activities. The staff support will be split with approximately 60% dedicated to activities funded through the Arctic Natural Sciences program and 40% dedicated to activities funded by the Arctic Social Sciences Program.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

ARCUS provides organizational support and science planning coordination and facilitates research community planning activities for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section. The additional activities planned under this major task are in support of the Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program.

2.2 ARCSS Program Coordination

ARCUS continues to provide community science management and coordination of activities for the NSF Arctic System Science (ARCSS) Program. With the guidance of the ARCSS Committee, the ARCSS Program is in transition from a focus on synthesis activities to targeted thematic efforts addressing arctic system issues. Program coordination activities reported below have been designed to sustain an effective synthesis effort and facilitate a smooth transition to new activities by fostering high levels of community input and strong interdisciplinary collaboration.

The requested supplementary funds will support convening and following up on the ARCSS-sponsored workshop *Arctic System Synthesis Workshop: New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling* in April 2007, planning and convening an ARCSS Committee meeting in May 2007, and ongoing science management office activities such as eTown meetings, teleconferences, and website maintenance.

Accomplishments

- Worked with the ARCSS Committee to organize and convene two online "eTown Meetings:" one in September 2006 to solicit community input on the ARCSS science planning process, attended by over 50 participants, and one in March 2007 to discuss priorities and strategies for ARCSS data management for promoting arctic system-level understanding and synthesis, attended by 48 participants.
- Organized the ARCSS Committee face-to-face meeting in November 2006; worked with the ARCSS Committee Executive Committee and NSF Program Director to develop the agenda, meeting materials, and facilitate meeting discussions.
- Supported three ARCSS meetings of opportunity at the 2006 American Geophysical Union (AGU) Conference in San Francisco through logistics, organizational, and website assistance.
- Supported emerging Communities of Practice—groups of researchers organized around a set of arctic system science questions—with planning and community development, including teleconference/webconference support and creation of online collaboration tools.
- Provided support for the group of funded Synthesis of Arctic System Science (SASS) projects/investigators, including support of individual project teleconferences, organization of several online meetings, and planning and providing materials for a special session at AGU in December 2006.
- Provided support for group of funded Study of the Northern Alaska Coastal System (SNACS) projects, including implementing a subcontract with the Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory (CRREL) to support a SNACS synthesis coordinator, updating and hosting of website, planning and providing materials for a special session at AGU in December 2006, and other meeting planning assistance.
- Provided support and guidance, through a subcontract with the University of Alaska Fairbanks, for a Human Dimensions of the Arctic System (HARC) project office to promote community development and coordinate human dimension research activities relevant to arctic system research.

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- Organized and convened several ARCSS Committee teleconferences on topics such as science planning, synthesis, and data management.
 - Supported and assisted the ARCSS Committee chair in planning, guiding, advising and leading the ARCSS Program community science planning and synthesis process.

Planned Activities; Supplemental Funds Requested

- In collaboration with the ARCSS Committee NSF ARCSS Program Director, SEARCH Program leadership, and the International Arctic Research Center, convene and support a three-day workshop on developing a coordinated data and modeling strategy to enhance arctic system synthesis; the workshop, *Arctic System Synthesis Workshop: New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling* will be held 2-4 April 2007 in Seattle, WA, will be streamed live, and will allow e-participation by community members unable to participate in person. Funds are also requested to follow up on the workshop's results with organizing committee teleconferences and staff support to develop and publish the workshop report.
- In collaboration with the ARCSS Committee and NSF Program Director, organize and convene May 2007 ARCSS Committee Meeting in Washington, DC.
- Ongoing science management office activities such as organization and support of community eTown Meetings, teleconferences, and website maintenance.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series

ARCUS implemented the Arctic Visiting Speakers' (AVS) Series in January 2000 to increase communication and collaboration among the dispersed arctic research community, to nurture understanding and communication between arctic researchers and arctic community residents, and to improve public understanding of arctic research.

The program accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through June 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support Arctic Visiting Speakers' tours from April through June 2007.

Accomplishments

- Ten AVS tours have taken place since April 2006, addressing arctic issues at 34 different events. Speakers presented at a variety of venues including visitor centers, museums, schools, workshops, cultural festivals, and on the radio.
- Over 1150 people attended the public presentations.
- Of the ten speaking tours, eight U.S. speakers visited institutions within the U.S. and two U.S. speakers traveled to Finland and Norway to lecture.
- Topics included the measurement of greenhouse gases in Alaska, permafrost, the state of climate change science, Native perspectives on western science and environmentalism, history and culture of Vikings, traditional wisdom and marine mammals in the context of climate change and industrialized fishing, multiculturalism in the European Arctic, and the environmental fate of trace metals in the Arctic.
- Eight new speakers were added to the Speaker's Bureau, which currently has 60 profiles

for potential Arctic Visiting Speakers.

- Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series brochures were distributed at various conferences.

Planned Activities; Supplemental Funding Requested

- Support up to four additional speaker tours through June 2007. One tour is already approved for mid-April.
- Continue to promote the use of the Arctic Visiting Speakers' Series to facilitate collaboration and information sharing about arctic research and the Arctic, including distribution of program information via ArcticInfo.
- Advertise the AVS series extensively among arctic residents; encourage participation by indigenous experts as visiting speakers and by arctic communities as host institutions.
- Post AVS information to several educational e-mail listserves around the country to stimulate interest from the K-12 education community to apply as host institutions.
- Continue to recruit individuals for the Speakers' Bureau.
- Continue to provide updated information about speaker tours on the ARCUS website.
- Post presentation videos and other materials sent to ARCUS by host institutions and speakers on the Internet Media Archive.

3.5 PolarTREC (Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating)

The PolarTREC (Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating) program is an educational research experience in which K-12 teachers participate in polar research, working closely with scientists as a pathway to improving science education through teachers' experiences in scientific inquiry. Participating teachers serve as a foundation for a growing community of students, educators, researchers and the general public that is engaged in science teaching and learning. Through PolarTREC, teachers will have the opportunity to increase their knowledge, enhance teaching skills, transfer their experiences to the classroom, engage in leadership roles, and develop a supportive network of researchers and education colleagues. NSF has awarded funds to ARCUS to support 36 PolarTREC expeditions for three years (2007–2009); supplemental funding is requested to support coordination of additional science education activities related to PolarTREC that will extend the influence and accessibility of the program, but which are not funded through the PolarTREC grant. These activities include staff support and travel for several researcher/teacher visits, additional school participation, and community networking.

Planned Activities; Supplemental Funds Requested

- Support teacher/researcher teams in planning and implementing education and outreach activities before, during, and after the field expedition.
- Provide travel support for researchers to visit classrooms.

4. INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletter

Witness the Arctic is a biannual newsletter, available online and in hardcopy, that provides information on current arctic research and education efforts and news, significant research

initiatives, national policy affecting arctic science, research support and logistics, profiles of institutions with major arctic research efforts, and calendar events and publications. With edited contributions from representatives throughout the arctic research and education community, *Witness the Arctic* is a substantive and significant source of information.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through June 2007 are listed below. Supplemental funding will support the newsletter planning and development from April through June 2007.

Accomplishments

- Completed the Spring 2006 (Volume 12, number 1) issue of the newsletter. Distributed to 6,100 U.S. and 4,000 international subscribers. The newsletter featured an article on closing the gap between scientific research and education, as well as the standard sections on NSF programs and activities, science news, and international news.
- In addition to the initial distribution to subscribers, the electronic version was posted on the ARCUS website for download; hard copies are available and distributed in response to requests.
- Planned contents, solicited contributions, edited submissions, and drafted material for Volume 12, number 2. The feature article for this issue is on the history of the International Polar Years. The expected publication date for Volume 12, number 2 is early April 2007. Estimated distribution will be to 6,500 U.S. and 4,225 international subscribers; the electronic version will be available for download.

Planned activities; Supplemental Funds Requested

- Begin work on Volume 13, number 1. Determine feature story topic, solicit contributions for all sections, edit submissions, and draft material for this issue. Expected publication date is March 2008.

4.2 Website/Internet Resources

The ARCUS website provides essential information and resources for the diverse and geographically distributed arctic research community and serves over 6,000 files from over 2,000 pages. The website is the focal point for web-served educational programs such as PolarTREC, various community science planning tools, and provides important information and resources to the research community about key research programs, meetings, community activities, and publications. The ARCUS website represents a valuable source of information for the general public about arctic research, a forum for scientific exchange among arctic researchers, approaches for integrating arctic research with educational programs, and access to other researchers, programs, and stakeholders working in the Arctic.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through June 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing website development, management and maintenance from April through June 2007.

Accomplishments

- Created, maintained, and updated sections of the website for ARCUS-facilitated programs, meetings, and workshops described in other activity descriptions in this report.

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- Posted on-line versions of various arctic research publications for community access and downloading.
 - Improved file structure and site architecture for major sections of the website.
 - Developed additional stylesheets for improved consistency in visual layout.
 - Implemented new technology and software for bulletin board applications (e.g., PolarTREC Virtual Base Camp) for improved security and user functionality.
 - Improved database-driven solutions (using SQL and PHP) with improved searchability and data sorting functionality for use in applications such as the Internet Media Archive, searchable project databases and a publication database.
 - Continued to improve accessibility standards and code-compliance throughout the website.
 - Transitioned the online Calendar maintained by ARCUS to a collaborative Arctic Calendar, working jointly with the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and the Arctic Ocean Sciences Board.
 - Developed an online calendar event submission process, with an underlying database that can be accessed and managed by any of the collaborating organizations.
 - Designed and implemented a unifying Arctic Calendar banner and footer that includes the logos of the sponsoring organizations and which can be used on linking or forwarding web pages on collaborating websites.

Planned Activities

- Make final design and function revisions to the Arctic Calendar website and database, fully implement the joint Arctic calendar, and announce its availability to the research community.
- Ongoing improvement to file structure and site architecture for efficient management of website.
- Ongoing development of database and community workspace tools as needed for a variety of programs and activities.
- Development of design and code standards to increase consistency throughout sections of the website.
- Ongoing development and update of content as needed.

4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver

ARCUS developed and manages the ArcticInfo Listserver, a "broadcast only" list with high quality, accuracy-checked, and well-edited content that provides information and important announcements to the international arctic research community. There have been 2,831 announcements distributed from ArcticInfo since its creation in September 1996. Each year has seen an increase in submissions for distribution and in subscribers. Currently about half of the subscribers are from the United States and half from other countries.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through June 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing management and maintenance from April through June 2007.

Accomplishments

- Received, reviewed, accepted or declined, edited, and formatted over 600 submissions to ArcticInfo.
- Distributed 490 announcements from April 2006 to present, including notices on funding opportunities, important events, publications, and position announcements. On average, approximately 40 announcements were posted per month.
- Communicated with subscribers regarding announcements, special information requests, subscribe or unsubscribe requests, and other concerns.
- Maintained a searchable online archive of all posted announcements.
- The listserv had 535 new subscribers in this period, resulting in 5,655 current subscribers.
- Maintained a database to track subscription activity.
- Managed the "bounce list" by researching bounced announcements to correct and update addresses, investigate apparently dead domains, and delete addresses that consistently bounced back from the subscriber list.
- In addition to managing ArcticInfo, ARCUS has created and manages 16 additional electronic lists for the arctic research community. These lists range from small group lists for community planning groups or science steering committees to large "community of researcher" lists, similar to but less comprehensive than ArcticInfo. Some of the lists are "participatory," meaning that any subscribed participant can post to the lists, and some are "broadcast only," meaning that only designated people can post content to the lists.

Planned Activities

- Continue to review, edit, and format ArcticInfo submissions. Post new announcements to the list and add them to the online archive.
- Continue to communicate with subscribers and organizations and individuals who wish to use the list for information distribution or access.
- Continue to track subscription activity and research "bounced" addresses.
- Continue advertising, maintenance, and management of the list.
- Continue to manage the additional arctic research community lists and develop additional lists, as needed and requested.

4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers

The Directory of Arctic Researchers was initiated in 1994 to aid links among individual investigators, institutions, funding agencies, and arctic stakeholders and to facilitate arctic research and education efforts. The contents of the directory have been developed through extensive surveys of individual arctic researchers and institutions.

The accomplishments since April 2006, and planned activities from now through June 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing management and maintenance of the Directory from April through June 2007.

Accomplishments

- Added 348 new records since April 2005. Presently there are a total of 4,309 individual records in the Directory.
- Surveyed researchers with current Directory records to obtain updated contact and current research information.
- Surveyed significant international research organizations and individuals to expand non-U.S. researcher records in the database.
- Maintained and regularly updated a downloadable PDF of the Directory, including alphabetically listed individual researcher entries and a cross-reference file listing researchers within science specialty categories. Developed a new Directory PDF design and creation process, which streamlined the PDF creation and results in a smaller file size.
- Developed a customized PDF creation option, which allows users to easily create a customized PDF of their Directory search returns.

Planned Activities

- Implement an automated daily update of the online Directory, which will include an automated daily Directory PDF creation and uploading process.
- Develop web services to allow interactions (pulling and pushing information) with other arctic databases such as the CEON-IMS, Barrow Area Information Database-Internet Map Server, and the VECO Polar Resources ARLSS project database.
- Develop and populate a new directory section for educators, which includes identifying individuals and groups for inclusion, sending survey forms, updating individual records for the database, and developing new search features on the Directory website.
- Continue maintenance and expansion of the on-line Directory.

4.5 Internet Media Archive

The ARCUS Internet Media Archive (IMA) is a collection of photos, graphics, videos, and presentations that have been compiled for various purposes and are now shared through the Internet via the IMA. The contents of the IMA are organized by the contributor's name, by event, or by organization. All of the media available in the archive are accompanied by information about the content, the contributor or source, and usage requirements.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through June 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support ongoing management and maintenance of the Internet Media Archive from April through June 2007.

Accomplishments

- Since April 2006, 3183 files have been added to the Internet Media Archive, which currently contains 6170 photos and other media resources available to the public in 100 albums and 33 categories. These resources have been viewed 40,212 times. An additional approximately 7,903 resources in the archive are not yet publicly available. Further documentation is being entered or gathered for these resources and when the information is complete they also will become publicly accessible.

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- Archived the majority of the extensive ARCUS collection of audio and video resources from various workshops and scientific meetings and education and outreach activities from 2001 to the present.
 - Posted all photos for which permission has been received to the online archive, with detailed photo information, photographer contact information, use criteria, and keywords for the search interface.

Planned Activities

- Periodically remind the research community of the availability of the Internet Media Archive via ArcticInfo and other listserves.
- Continue to gather and add to the collection of arctic-related images and other media resources and continue research and data entry of relevant information about source, subject, dates, research project, and funding source for all of the images.
- Maintain communication with the contributors and potential contributors to solicit contributions and timely and detailed information about the media resources.
- Continue video- and audio-recording of relevant meetings, workshops, and programmatic activities for inclusion in the Internet Media Archive.
- Obtain use permissions, attribution, and detailed information for the entire ARCUS image collection.
- Identify or produce additional figures, photographs, and maps depicting arctic research-related information. Develop short abstracts that explain each scientific figure and that provide information necessary for attribution, as well as citations for source material and other related references.

4.6 Arctic Community Outreach

ARCUS conducts a number of outreach activities that disseminate timely information about arctic research to scientists, policy and decision-makers, educators and the public, and that build supportive networks among those groups to advance international arctic research efforts and our understanding of the Arctic as a region.

The accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through June 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support outreach activities from April through June 2007, primarily the *Arctic Forum 2007* scheduled for May 2007, for which planning has already begun.

Accomplishments

- Planned and hosted the 1.5-day *Arctic Forum* conference in conjunction with ARCUS' 18th Annual Meeting in Washington, D.C. in May 2006. The topic of the *Forum* was "International Arctic Research at a Turning Point: Innovations and Collaborations for the Future," a theme that directly built on the topic and success of *Arctic Forum 2005*. The *Forum* was co-chaired by Dr. Craig Tweedie of the University of Texas El Paso and Dr. Volker Rachold of the International Arctic Science Committee. A two-minute video was developed by ARCUS staff in Spring 2006 with material from past *Arctic Forum* sessions to advertise *Arctic Forum 2006* and was distributed via the ARCUS website. *Arctic Forum 2006* was announced to the international arctic research community and

registration and abstract submissions solicited via ArcticInfo and *Witness the Arctic*.

- *Arctic Forum 2006* attracted 136 participants and included arctic researchers from the U.S. and nine other countries, policy makers, media representatives, federal agency personnel, and arctic residents, including significant representation from indigenous arctic communities.
 - The *Forum* was video-streamed via the Internet and followed by an international audience beyond those in attendance in Washington, D.C. Participants viewing the Forum via the video-stream were able to email questions and comments for the presenters to the co-chairs and ARCUS staff for inclusion in session discussions.
 - Plenary, panel, and poster presentations and discussions addressed topics such as: challenges and needs of system scale science; challenges and needs of stakeholder and community partnerships;; broadening the legacy of the International Polar Year; and advancing arctic research through policy and science advocacy.
 - Presentations from the meeting are available on the ARCUS *Arctic Forum* website as downloadable Powerpoint or PDF files. Edited video and audio files from the *Arctic Forum 2006* presentations and sessions are available on the Internet Media Archive.
- Developed information resources such as flyers, brochures, and posters regarding arctic research activities and priorities; participated in outreach activities at scientific meetings and workshops to inform the broader scientific community and policy and decision-makers about important arctic research efforts and findings.
 - Participated in or sponsored arctic outreach activities at the October 2006 AAAS Arctic Science Conference in Fairbanks, Alaska, the Fall 2006 Meeting of AGU in San Francisco, California, and at other relevant meetings and workshops.

Planned Activities

- Convene a 1.5-day *Arctic Forum* in conjunction with ARCUS' 19th Annual Meeting in Washington, DC in May 2007. The focus of the *Arctic Forum 2006* will be "Water in the Arctic: International Collaborations and Understanding Environmental Change." The *Arctic Forum* is timed to coincide with a special program at the Embassy of Sweden on "Water and Environment," which offers reflections on global, national, regional, and local perspectives regarding water. Forum sessions will include a diverse and international range of perspectives on the state of knowledge of the hydrological cycle in the circumpolar Arctic, gaps in our knowledge, and research and policy opportunities and priorities. The *Arctic Forum* sessions will highlight international collaborations for the International Polar Year and beyond. Presentations and discussions will focus on questions such as: What are the changes being witnessed in the water cycle and how will these changes impact the physical, biological, and social environments of the Arctic? How does the science of water and the arctic environment relate to public policy and how can information be translated to decision makers? How can we forge international collaborations during IPY and beyond to address these exciting scientific challenges and opportunities? The *Arctic Forum 2007* will be co-chaired by Larry Hinzman, University of Alaska Fairbanks, and Gunhild Rosqvist, Stockholm University.

-
- Publish and distribute the 2006 *Arctic Forum* abstract volume.
 - Prepare posters or presentations on request and participate in major scientific meetings or workshops to provide information and outreach regarding arctic research activities, needs, and priorities.

5. CORE SUPPORT

Core support provides management and infrastructure crucial to support the overall tasks and the projects and activities included in each task of the cooperative agreement. This category was initiated to ensure stability and continuity of the direct activities that support the whole of the cooperative agreement so they are not vulnerable to the changes in the specific tasks and activities funded from year-to-year throughout the agreement.

ARCUS is a relatively small non-profit organization, and the Executive Director is closely involved in all activities of the organization including planning, prioritizing, managing, and directly implementing the work undertaken on behalf of the National Science Foundation. The Executive Director works closely with ARCUS project managers to prioritize tasks with respect to annual and longer-term plans and to manage individual workloads and projects. She closely reviews activities and products and ensures that projects are completed as scheduled and in accordance with the annual plan and that the products or effects of the activities are beneficial to arctic research and to the goals of the particular task funded through the cooperative agreement. She is directly involved in working with science steering committees and research community contributors to ensure that projects are concluded effectively and in a timely fashion. The Executive Director also works closely with the ARCUS Business Manager in budgeting and reviewing ongoing project expenditures against the NSF budget. The Executive Director liaises directly with NSF on all planning, programmatic, and budget issues. This component of management is essential to the ongoing work ARCUS carries out on behalf of NSF.

Similarly, the Systems Administrator manages the network, server, and all technical needs required to support NSF tasks and project activities. He works directly with the Executive Director to ensure that all hardware and software requirements are met so that server and network operations supporting NSF activities are carried out smoothly and efficiently. The Executive Director and Systems Administrator plan for upcoming needs, including scientific meetings and conferences convened by ARCUS on behalf of the NSF, in conjunction with the annual program plan.

While the work of both these positions is directly related to the successful implementation of NSF activities and projects, it is more difficult to allocate much of this time specifically to any one individual project, hence the use of Core Support to collect these direct management costs. Other costs charged to Core Support include direct system infrastructure (computer hardware and software required to maintain the network and server for the databases and listserves that support NSF-funded activities), high-speed Internet, and the development necessary to continuously maintain the level of service committed to the arctic research community under the cooperative agreement.

The major accomplishments since April 2006 and planned activities from now through June 2007 are listed below. The supplemental funds requested would support Core activities from April through June 2007.

Accomplishments

- Coordinated planning, managed emerging priorities, and supervised work on all the tasks and project activities described in this report. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category rather than to individual projects.
- Upgraded hardware, software, and programming to expand capability for projects that require expanded server, network, and database capacity, support for NSF-sponsored meeting online registration, poster submission, and general information distribution.
- Managed the server setup, network, creation of needed technical resources, and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement is charged to the Core Support category. System upgrades included:
 - Performed Web server backend upgrades for PHP and MySQL plus applications relying on those packages.
 - Overhauled the email server spam prevention system, switching to the ASSP (Anti-Spam SMTP Proxy) software.
 - Overhauled and expanded the network backup system, including software upgrades and adding a backup server to greatly expand capacity.
 - Created multiple new email lists on the List Server machine and performed minor software upgrades on the server.
 - Replaced the Flexmail web email form processor (concerns included security and performance issues) with custom-built PHP form processor.
 - Performed a number of other software and hardware upgrades to increase system and network efficiency and security.
 - Researched, purchased, and set up an Epson 9600 large format printer, used for printing posters and banners for NSF-funded projects. The on-site availability of the large format printer has considerably reduced the cost of producing posters for various projects.
- Supported staff travel to arctic research meetings and workshops that addressed topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which were not specific to one project.

Planned Activities

- Coordinate planning, prioritization and supervision of work on all the tasks and projects described in the projected activities, the program plan and budget for 2007-2008. The portion of the Executive Director's time dedicated to project activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Continue to research and upgrade hardware, software and programming required to expand the interactive and dynamic capabilities of such projects as SEARCH, the ARCSS Program, the Arctic Social Sciences Program, PolarTREC, the Directory of Arctic Researchers, ArcticInfo, the collaborative Arctic Calendar, the Internet Media

Archive, interactive real-time online seminars and meetings, interactive bulletin boards, meeting registration and abstract submission, streamed audio and video content, and general information.

- Manage the server setup, network, and creation of needed technical resources and the computing capability that directly supports the project activities. The portion of the System Administrator's time dedicated to direct activities funded through this agreement will be charged to the Core Support category.
- Support staff participation at arctic research meetings and workshops on topics pertaining to multiple NSF projects and activities included in the cooperative agreement, but which are not specific to one project.

SUMMARY

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research efforts for over fifteen years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents that reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. All of the activities described in this request for supplemental funds support the community science planning process for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section and provide information and support for the conduct of arctic research and, therefore, will contribute to the overall excellence and advancement of arctic research supported by the National Science Foundation.

Supplement Request Justification

This supplement of \$633,392 to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. ARC-0101279) is necessary to continue support of ongoing activities that are within the scope of the original agreement while details of a new cooperative agreement are negotiated. This supplement request also extends the expiration date of the award from 31 March 2007 to 30 June 2007 so that there will be no interruption of ongoing services and current tasking prior to a new award being made.

All of the activities described in the Summary of Proposed Work and the Budget Justification are in keeping with, and part of, ARCUS' work with the National Science Foundation to provide organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs. The specific activities and the support that will be provided have been discussed with the NSF managing program officer. All activities are within the scope of the current cooperative agreement and are described in detail in the Summary of Proposed Work.

ARCUS submitted a proposal for a five-year cooperative agreement (CA) on 24 January 2006; we understand that NSF has completed the review process and intends to recommend a new cooperative agreement with ARCUS. The NSF Office of Polar Programs (OPP) is negotiating the budget details of a new CA with ARCUS and, for the first time, the Division of Arctic Sciences will need to take the ARCUS CA proposal to the Directors Review Board (DRB) for approval, due to a reduction in the amount of the DRB threshold.

The managing program officer notified ARCUS in March 2007 that the process would not be completed in time to seamlessly transition ARCUS to a new CA. It is important to ARCUS and OPP that ARCUS continue progress on current tasking while the new CA is negotiated. The managing program officer requested that ARCUS submit a request for a three-month supplemental budget to extend the existing CA to the date when a new CA will be awarded so that there will be no interruption of ongoing services and current tasking.

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	2.25	0.00	0.00	\$ 19,000			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	2.25	0.00	0.00	19,000			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (9) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	3.00	0.00	0.00	82,200			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				2,800			
5. (5) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				19,500			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					123,500		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					46,930		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					170,430		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					0		
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)					38,500		
2. FOREIGN					0		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____			600				
2. TRAVEL _____			56,000				
3. SUBSISTENCE _____			50,500				
4. OTHER _____			0				
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (60) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS					107,100		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				16,650			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				7,500			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				10,800			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				6,000			
5. SUBAWARDS				0			
6. OTHER				102,000			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					142,950		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					458,980		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect on Total Direct - Subcontracts (Rate: 38.0000, Base: 458980)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					174,412		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					633,392		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				\$	633,392	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - Executive Director	2.25	0.00	0.00	\$ 19,000			
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	2.25	0.00	0.00	19,000			
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0			
2. (9) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	3.00	0.00	0.00	82,200			
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS				0			
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS				2,800			
5. (5) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)				19,500			
6. (0) OTHER				0			
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)				123,500			
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)				46,930			
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)				170,430			
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT				0			
E. TRAVEL				38,500			
1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							
2. FOREIGN				0			
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____	600						
2. TRAVEL _____	56,000						
3. SUBSISTENCE _____	50,500						
4. OTHER _____	0						
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (60)				TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS	107,100		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES				16,650			
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION				7,500			
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES				10,800			
4. COMPUTER SERVICES				6,000			
5. SUBAWARDS				0			
6. OTHER				102,000			
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS				142,950			
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)				458,980			
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)				174,412			
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)				633,392			
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)				0			
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				\$ 633,392			
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

C *ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES REQUIRED FOR REVISED BUDGET

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. ARC-0101279). The supplement of \$633,392 to the funding already awarded is necessary to extend the expiration date of the award to 30 June 2007.

All of the activities described are in keeping with and part of ARCUS' work for the National Science Foundation (NSF) providing organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs.

ARCUS is submitting this supplement request to continue activities at the request of and on behalf of NSF and the arctic research community, and other participants in and managers of arctic research programs. The activities and support to be provided have been discussed with the relevant NSF program managers.

Item A: Senior Personnel

Funding totaling \$19,000 for current staff through 30 June 2007 is requested.

Item B: Other Personnel

Resources are requested for a total of 15 staff positions for three additional months. Personnel salaries and benefits required to continue to develop, coordinate, and manage continuing activities total \$104,500.

Item C: Fringe Benefits

ARCUS charges actual fringe benefits costs on direct salaries. The fringe rate for budgeting purpose is 38% and totals \$46,930.

Items E and F: Travel and Participant Support

Additional resources are requested to support participation in several upcoming meetings: the April 2007 ARCSS Data/Modeling workshop, the May 2007 ARCSS Committee meeting, and the May 2007 *Arctic Forum*. Support is requested for a total 75 attendees at a cost of \$145,600.

Item G: Other Direct Costs

Line 1. Materials and Supplies

Resources totaling \$16,650 are requested to support typical materials costs for a three-month period.

Line 2. Publication/Documentation and Dissemination

Publication and distribution costs for documents such as the report for *Arctic System Synthesis Workshop: New Perspectives through Data Discovery and Modeling*, and the *Arctic Forum abstract volume* total \$7,500.

Line 3. Consultant Services

Consultant services costs totaling \$10,800 will support the ARCSS Committee, providing a renewal of the annual stipend for the ARCSS Committee chair.

Line 4. Computer Services

Computer support services totaling \$6,000 are anticipated under Core Support.

Line 5. Subcontracts

No additional funds are requested for subcontracts.

Line 6. Other

Resources totaling \$102,000 are requested to cover the cost of conference meeting support and other miscellaneous expenses for participants at the April 2007 ARCSS synthesis workshop, the May 2007 ARCSS Committee meeting, and the May 2007 *Arctic Forum*.

Item I: Indirect Costs (rate/base)

The ARCUS maximum provisional rate is currently 38%. The current ARCUS NSF cooperative agreement allows charging of indirect costs to Participant Support, which has been kept in the base of \$458,980.

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
 OPP-0101279
 NSF Program Summary

Attachment C

4/10/07 19:57

1-Apr-07
 30-Jun-07
Budget

Form 1030 Category

Salaries

President	A1	-
Executive director	A2	19,000
Other professionals	B2	82,200
Student	B3	2,800
Clerical	B5	19,500
Total salaries		<u>123,500</u>

Fringe Benefits

Total salaries and fringe benefits	C	<u>46,930</u>
		170,430

Permanent Equipment

	D	-
--	---	---

Travel (domestic)

	E1	38,500
--	----	--------

Travel (foreign)

	E2	-
--	----	---

Participant Support Costs

Stipends	F1	600
Travel	F2	56,000
Subsistence	F3	50,500
Total participant costs		<u>107,100</u>

Other Direct Costs

Materials and supplies	G1	16,650
Publication cost/ docum/dissem	G2	7,500
Consultant services	G3	10,800
Computer services	G4	6,000
Subcontracts	G5	-
Other	G6	102,000
Total other direct costs		<u>142,950</u>

Total direct costs	H	458,980
--------------------	---	---------

Indirect

	I	174,412
--	---	---------

TOTAL	J	633,392
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Summary - Supplement Request ARC-0101279

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION

4/10/07 19:57 4/1/2007 to 06/30/07

1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING	
1.1 Arctic Logistics	
1.2 Alias Website	
1.3 GIS Planning	
1.4a SEARCH Planning	12350
1.4b SEARCH OSM Student Support	
1.5 Bering Sea Planning	2690
1.6 Workshop TBD	
1.7 SEARCH Brochure	
1.8 Arctic Data Coordination	
Subtotal Direct Costs	<u>15040</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>5715</u>
	<u>20755</u>
2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION	
2.1 Arctic Section Science Materials	0
2.2 <i>ARCSS Program Coordination</i>	
2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination	129920
2.2.2 ARCSS All-Hands Workshop	
2.2.3 HARC SMO	
2.2.4 Arctic Hydrology Report	
Subtotal 2.2 Direct Costs	<u>129920</u>
2.3 <i>ASSP Program Coordination</i>	
2.3.1 Arctic Social Sciences Planning	
2.3.2 Greenland Book	
2.3.3 Arctic Social Sciences Volume	
2.3.4 Bering Sea Community Planning	
Subtotal 2.3 Direct Costs	<u>0</u>
Sub-total Direct Costs	129920
Indirect Costs	<u>49370</u>
	<u>179290</u>
3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION	
3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	8770
3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers	5100
3.3 Arctic Science Education Report	
3.4 ARCTIC ALIVE!	
3.5 TREC	
Subtotal Direct Costs	<u>13870</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>5271</u>
	<u>19141</u>
4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH	
4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters	10350
4.2 Website/ Internet Resources	27600
4.3 ArcticInfo Listserver	7866
4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers	990
4.5 Internet Media Archive	6900
4.6 Arctic Community Outreach	174594
4.7 Publication: The Arctic	
4.8 Endangered Species Bulletin	
Subtotal Direct Costs	<u>228300</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>86754</u>
	<u>315054</u>
5 CORE SUPPORT	
Core Support	<u>71850</u>
Subtotal Direct Costs	<u>0</u>
Indirect Costs	<u>27302</u>
	<u>99152</u>
TOTAL	<u>633392</u>
Estimated Indirect Cost Rate	38.00%

**Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
Budget Explanation - Supplement Request ARC-0101279**

**4/1/2007 to
06/30/07**

1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.4a SEARCH Planning

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	10,350
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	2,000
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>12,350</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>4,693</u>
	<u>17,043</u>

1.5 Bering Sea Planning

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	690
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	2,000
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>2,690</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>1,022</u>
	<u>3,712</u>

Subtotal Direct	15,040
Subtotal Indirect	5,715
Total Community Science Planning	<u>20,755</u>

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
Budget Explanation - Supplement Request ARC-0101279
4/1/2007 to

2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION
ARCSS PROGRAM COORDINATION

2.2.1 ARCSS Coordination	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	26,220
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	18,000
Participant Support Costs	42,000
Materials and Supplies	200
Publications/Dissemination	1,500
Consulting	10,500
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	31,500
Total direct costs	<u>129,920</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>49,370</u>
	<u>179,290</u>
Subtotal Direct Costs	129,920
Subtotal Indirect Costs	49,370
Total Arctic Sciences Section	<u>179,290</u>

3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 Arctic Science Education Activities	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	5,520
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	3,000
Materials and Supplies	250
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>8,770</u>
Total indirect cost	<u>3,333</u>
	<u>12,103</u>

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
Budget Explanation - Supplement Request ARC-0101279
4/1/2007 to

3.2 Arctic Visiting Speakers	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	5,100
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>5,100</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>1,938</u>
	<u>7,038</u>
Subtotal Direct Costs	13,870
Subtotal Indirect Costs	5,271
Total Arctic Science Education	<u>19,141</u>

4 INFORMATION AND OUTREACH

4.1 Witness the Arctic Newsletters	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	10,350
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>10,350</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>3,933</u>
	<u>14,283</u>

Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
Budget Explanation - Supplement Request ARC-0101279
4/1/2007 to

<u>4.2 ARCUS Internet Resources</u>	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	27,600
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>27,600</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>10,488</u>
	<u>38,088</u>
<u>4.3 ArcticInfo Listserv</u>	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	7,866
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>7,866</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>2,989</u>
	<u>10,855</u>
<u>4.4 Directory of Arctic Researchers</u>	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	690
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	300
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>990</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>376</u>
	<u>1,366</u>

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4.5 <u>Internet Media Archive</u>	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	6,900
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	<u>6,900</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>2,622</u>
	<u>9,522</u>
4.6 <u>Arctic Community Outreach</u>	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	29,394
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	13,000
Participant Support Costs	55,000
Materials and Supplies	1,200
Publications/Dissemination	6,000
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	70,000
Total direct costs	<u>174,594</u>
Total indirect costs	<u>66,346</u>
	<u>240,940</u>
Subtotal Direct	228,300
Subtotal Indirect	86,754
Total Information and Outreach	<u>315,054</u>

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5 CORE SUPPORT	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	44,850
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic/foreign)	5,500
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and supplies	15,000
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	6,000
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	500
Total direct costs	<u>71,850</u>
Total indirect costs	27,302
Total Core Support	<u>99,152</u>
Total Direct Costs all tasks	458,980
Total Indirect Costs all tasks	174,412
Total All Tasks	<u><u>633,392</u></u>

TOTAL	
Salaries and Fringe Benefits	170,430
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel	38,500
Participant Support Costs	107,100
Materials and Supplies	16,650
Publications/Dissemination	7,500
Consulting	10,800
Computer Services	6,000
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	102,000
Total direct costs	<u>458,980</u>
Indirect Costs @ 38.0%	174,412
Total direct and indirect	<u><u>633,392</u></u>